

Designing buildings for 3D concrete printing

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Abstract

3D concrete printing technologies are gaining momentum in the construction sector, although typical architectural building designs are not directly applicable to 3D printing. There is a lack of knowledge regarding 3D concrete printing technology among architects because they are not trained in designing buildings for this specific construction method. The good news is that designing and preparing such digital models for 3D printing is now easier than ever thanks to the cutting-edge technologies of modern 3D computer graphics.

The thesis provides an example of a building design and optimization methodology for 3D concrete printing from an architect's perspective. Using BIM authoring software like Autodesk Revit, architects are now more capable of creating and adapting a building design into a digital model suitable for 3D concrete printing. The method focuses on improving the shapes of geometrical elements by setting a construction strategy for each phase and, at the same time, preparing the BIM model for quick extraction of the printable digital model. Finally, the connection between the digital model and the materialized 3D-printed object is made by exporting and slicing the model using specific formats and software for the intended 3D printing machine.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/SVli1lViapM>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034048